

DRYING AND QUALITY STORAGE OF AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTS METHODS

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Abstract

In this article, based on the needs of the population of our country, we will talk about ways to dry agricultural products and measures to keep them in good quality throughout the year.

Keywords: fruits, vegetables, agriculture, products, processing, drying, drying, temporary storage, permanent storage, storage, technology.

Currently, practical and scientific researches are being carried out in depth on the technology of primary processing and quality storage of fruits and vegetables, grain and grain products, technical crops, and agricultural products in general.

The degree of product processing can be different, that is, primary processing or deep processing. While primary processing includes simple operations such as drying, deep processing includes operations such as processing the product at several stages, i.e. canning, juicing, and packaging.

For example, if we take deep drying of fruit, this process consists of the following stages: O'rik (turk) drying. The following varieties of O'rik are considered sour: Yubileiny Navoi, Korsodiq, Komsomolsky, Isfarak, Khandon, Gulongi almonds, Turshak preparation technique. Turshak is a dried apricot with seeds. The brought fruits are separated (sorted) into varieties depending on their size. Various calibration machines are used for this purpose. Apricots are sorted according to the level of ripeness, because the mode of raw material processing - smoking, drying depends on the level of ripeness of fruits. Apricots to be dried are washed to remove dust and mud. The O'rik is blanched in boiling water or in a solution. This work speeds up the smoking and drying processes with gold matches. Keyu fruits are immediately placed in a row on wooden trays and sent to the smoking chamber. Smoking requires 2-2.5 grams of sulfur per 1 kg of product and 1.5 hours. Smoked fruits are dried in the open for 3-4 days. After 2 days, the fruits are turned over. In total, drying takes days. Drying is complete when the fruits dry evenly and the skin does not separate. Narni is brought to 16%, the products are placed in cardboard boxes with a capacity of one kilogram or in kraft bags. The product is stored in warehouses with a temperature of 0-10 °C, relative humidity of 60-65 percent.

Preparation of apricot fruit (kaysa) technology. Kaysa is a pitted and dried apricot. It is made from large apricot fruits. Which one the preparation technique is almost the same as making turshak doesn't make a difference. For example: smoked in patais the fruits are placed in the drying area and they Bandi after putting a little in a day or two the skin is removed from the incision on the side and again it is collected in trays and placed in the open area. One or two after a day, the fruits are dried in the shade. Next the work is no different from making a stew. It ripens in 8-13 days, 20-27 percent of the raw material a dry product is obtained.

Permanent warehouses are made of concrete or brick in the shape of a one-story right angle and above or deeper than the ground (1.5-2 m). When choosing storage methods for each type of product, location conditions and available storage volumes are taken into account. For example, depending on different weather conditions, the size of the pile and trench for storing potatoes may be different. When setting up a temporary warehouse, depending on the type and quantity of products, how many piles or piles are needed, construction measures, placing and covering the products on them, and these are different for different agricultural products.

In conclusion, it should be said that the farm or entrepreneurs who plan to start processing should first of all ensure that there is a sufficient base of raw materials around them and based on the volume of available raw materials, they should purchase and install the processing. It is necessary to pay attention to the correct selection of the power of the equipment. Another key aspect is the question of the market for the manufactured product. That is, it is necessary to clearly plan whether the produced product will be sold in the foreign market (export) or in the domestic market. Due to the current conditions of our republic, all types of agricultural products can be processed and preserved for a certain period of time and in special ways.

References:

1. Kh.B.Shoumarov, S.Ya.Islamov. "Technology of storage and primary processing of agricultural products". Tashkent: "Innovation-Ziya", 2020.
2. H. Ch. Boriyev. O.A. Ashurmetov. Biology and cultivation and storage technology of polys crops. - T.: "Mehnat", 2000.
3. State register of agricultural crops recommended for cultivation in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Tashkent, 2006.
4. Behzod G., Su-Chin C., Tahir M. An Ecological Disaster of the Aral Sea //Journal of Soil and Water Conservation. - 2009.

